

2025

High Level Workshop

ON THE EUROPEAN RESEARCH AREA

*Research Collaboration, Competition,
Valorisation, and Protection in an
ERA of Uncertainty*

Oslo, 18–20 November 2025

Event Report

UK Research
and Innovation

Research Council
of Norway

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High Level Workshop

ON THE EUROPEAN RESEARCH AREA

UK Research
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Introduction

THIS REPORT SUMMARISES the discussions that took place between 18–20 November, in Oslo, Norway, at the 17th Science Europe High Level Workshop on ERA. This workshop was co-organised with the Norwegian Research Council (RCN) and UK Research and Innovation (UKRI).

The 2025 workshop was entitled ‘Research Collaboration, Competition, Valorisation, and Protection in an ERA of Uncertainty’. Its goal was to reflect on relevant and urgent topics not only related to research and innovation (R&I) policy in isolation, but to how R&I is part of a globally interconnected network. To achieve this, the sessions addressed:

- ✦ International research collaboration in light of geopolitical challenges.
- ✦ The balance between research security and openness, and the important role of Horizon-associated countries.
- ✦ The upcoming 10th EU Framework Programme for R&I, Horizon Europe.
- ✦ The case study of polar research, which illustrates the above key topics.

On the first day of the workshop, a wide range of contributors delivered high-level keynote speeches and engaged with participants during plenary sessions. On the second day, the discussions focused on two themes: ‘Valorisation and Innovation’ and ‘Shaping the Future of Research’. Each theme consisted of keynote speeches and a panel discussion. Participants further discussed these issues during parallel breakout sessions.

In total, 80 participants from 49 organisations in 26 countries contributed to the event, including senior leaders from the research funding and performing organisations that make up Science Europe, national- and European-level policy makers, researchers, and other stakeholders from the wider research community.

During the discussions at the workshop, crucial themes emerged. These did not only relate to the nature of research and innovation, but also to the role of research in geopolitics and international collaboration. Participants recognised the need for an autonomous EU Framework Programme for R&I that supports open and secure international collaboration and remains connected (but not subordinated) to the competitiveness of Europe.

The nature of competitiveness itself should be understood in a more comprehensive manner and should encompass long-term, regenerative growth. An autonomous R&I system, capable of responsible self-governance, is essential for this. At the same time, the challenges of – and necessary trade-offs for – equitable and open, yet secure, international collaboration should be acknowledged. Furthermore, the next Horizon Europe programme and its links to other programmes (such as the European Competitiveness Fund), must enable the participation of Associated Countries, which will be key to the programme’s success.

The [Concluding Statement](#) of the event, published on 4 December, outlines these key themes. A summary of these is included in the conclusions of this report, together with the key themes that emerged from the breakout discussions outside of the plenary sessions.

From left to right: Ambassador Jan Thompson, Professors Mari Sundli Tveit and Christopher Smith, and Dr. Lidia Borrell-Damián, at the British Embassy in Oslo

Welcome Reception

THE WORKSHOP COMMENCED with a welcome reception, kindly hosted by and at the British Embassy in Oslo on the evening of 18 November. The British Ambassador, Jan Thompson, and professors Mari Sundli Tveit (Research Council of Norway, RCN) and Christopher Smith (UK Research and Innovation, UKRI), emphasised the importance of international collaboration in their welcome speeches, as well as the need to ensure that research and innovation are conducted in a safe, transparent, inclusive, and equitable manner for all partners.

They highlighted the support provided by Science Europe and its Member Organisations to strengthen Ukraine's research and innovation ecosystem, and the example of polar research to illustrate how international collaboration can drive scientific progress and address shared challenges in the face of geopolitical challenges and climate change.

The reception set the scene for discussions on the European Commission's draft proposal for Horizon Europe 2028–34 and how it can best support excellence, collaboration, openness, research security, and the long-term competitiveness of the European research and innovation system.

Welcome Addresses

THE MAIN PROCEEDINGS of the High Level Workshop were opened on 19 November by its co-hosts, the President of Science Europe, Mari Sundli Tveit (RCN), and Member of the Governing Board, Christopher Smith (UKRI). They welcomed participants to Oslo and the 17th edition of the event, and set the scene for the discussions ahead.

Highlighting the complex nature of the current R&I landscape, influenced by geopolitical, environmental, and societal disruptions, Tveit called on the gathered members of the research community to work together across disciplines, sectors, and nations to address these global challenges. She emphasised the important role of the upcoming 10th EU Framework Programme for R&I, Horizon Europe, stating that it should foster an R&I ecosystem that maintains its focus on excellence at all stages, supports innovation, and enables open collaboration within and beyond the EU. When building this ecosystem, the delicate balance between openness and security must be navigated: the former is essential to progress, but must be pursued with responsibility. She underlined the role of Science Europe as a forum to ensure that science remains free and is used for the benefit of society.

Smith confirmed the importance of the critical topics addressed by Tveit and addressed the case study of polar research. Referring to literary works, both scientific and poetic, he noted the Arctic's threefold relationship with science: while at first it was only a subject of research, it has also become its victim through the negative implications of technological progress on the climate. He expressed hope, however, that it would also be a future beneficiary of research. The Arctic example demonstrates the need to practice science in a responsible way and in a broader sense, to consider how science can contribute to peace, rather than to conflict. To do so, science should be applied according to the concept of *wissenschaft*, which includes all disciplines. He concluded his welcome speech by quoting the Norwegian poet Olav H. Hauge's work 'Ocean', drawing parallels with the depths and complexities of the research endeavour itself.

*“This is the ocean.
Vast and gray,
gravity itself.
Yet just as the mind
in solitary moments
suddenly opens
its shifting reflections
to secret depths—
so the ocean
one blue morning
can open itself
to sky and solitude.
See, the ocean gleams,
I, too, have stars
and blue depths.”*

—Olav H. Hauge (1951)

Keynote Speeches: Part 1

Sigrun Aasland

Echoing the themes invoked during the welcome speeches, **Sigrun Aasland**, the Norwegian Minister of Research and Higher Education, underscored that international collaboration is at the core of knowledge and research. She summarised the main challenge due to shifting global dynamics, acknowledging that “the values that we have taken for granted, are no longer to be taken for granted,” referring to the risks academic freedom is facing, and the increasing difficulty of achieving a consensus. Against this backdrop, she called for closer collaboration to build a “sustainable, safe and secure Europe for all.” She praised the commitment of the European research community, which has contributed to keeping the next Horizon Europe a standalone programme and to the realisation of other important initiatives, such as [Choose Europe](#).

Minister Aasland pointed out the need to align national and European priorities and the untapped potential of synergies between Horizon Europe and national programmes. She highlighted Norway’s commitment to fund Arctic and polar research as one of its key R&I priorities. Addressing research security, she referred to a white paper by the Norwegian government on the research system, which underscores the responsibility of both the research institution and the government to facilitate secure research conduct, together with additional national-level research security measures.

In this work, Norway acts in line with European priorities. However, balancing this with openness is a common interest, she stated, noting parallels between Norway’s talent recruitment initiative and Choose Europe.

She shared Norwegian perspectives on the upcoming Horizon Europe programme, welcoming the focus on competitiveness and the links with the European Competitiveness Fund (ECF) to support innovation. At the same time, she stressed the importance of the Framework Programme remaining self-standing, with its own ringfenced budget. She emphasised Norway’s commitment to contributing to European goals and responding to shared challenges. Therefore, Horizon Europe must allow for Norway’s full association, participation, and eligibility in all parts of the programme. She concluded on an optimistic note, observing that the Horizon Europe proposal seems promising, and will be further strengthened through continued co-operation. She regarded the High Level Workshop as an important opportunity to address these key questions.

Signe Ratso

Signe Ratso, Deputy Director General for Research and Innovation at the European Commission, presented the Commission’s perspectives. She also emphasised the importance of the Framework Programme being both self-standing and closely connected to the ECF, quoting the need to establish an innovation journey that

starts from blue-sky, fundamental research and lasts until deployment. She added that this outcome is the result of careful reflections on the feedback provided by all stakeholders, including the R&I community. She commended the successes of Horizon Europe, such as the international recognition of 'Horizon' as a brand, the record number of applicants to the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA), and the practical achievements of EU startups becoming 'unicorns', amongst others.

These successes, and its reciprocal openness, make Horizon Europe attractive for global partners, leading to association, she argued. She listed some of the 22 Associated Countries, citing that their association increases access to excellence, and leads to higher-quality publications. She highlighted the importance of association in context of the European Research Area (ERA), as well as its benefits to industrial innovation and competitiveness.

After briefly addressing the maintained pillar structure, increased budget, and widening-related reforms of the new Horizon Europe, she listed three innovations that characterise the programme:

- ▶ Its focus on competitiveness will be a key part of collaborative R&I, and should lead to solutions that improve citizens' lives. In addition, it will create tangible impact that can be used to combat scepticism towards science.
- ▶ The programme will be "dual use by default," because of the need to recognise the changed geopolitical situation, the increasingly blurred line between defence and civilian applications (especially so for fundamental research, where it is difficult to ascertain future applications), and the investment-related benefits of dual use.
- ▶ Renewed focus on simplification. The lack of details in the proposals is intended, as shorter and less prescriptive calls are the goal. She also mentioned the single rulebook, as well as practical, applicant-focused measures, including ones linked to digital transformation.

In conclusion, Ratso called on participants to create "an ecosystem where Europe's research excellence translates into global market leadership" and "conditions where talent can build the next generation of European Champions."

Manuel Heitor

The Chair of the Expert Group on the Interim Evaluation of Horizon Europe, **Manuel Heitor**, delivered his recommendations for the next Framework Programme, calling it a unique opportunity. Emphasising the reliability of the European R&I ecosystem, he argued that there is an 'investment gap', rather than an 'innovation gap'. Although the current Multiannual Financial Framework proposal is a good start, he reiterated that the budget should be at least €200bn, as Mario Draghi's [report](#) on improving the EU's competitiveness recommends – and ideally, it should be over €220bn, as outlined in the report '[Align, Act, Accelerate](#)' he co-ordinated. He also repeated his

call for a truly autonomous and effective 'standalone' Framework Programme, and encouraged the research community to increase its advocacy towards this end. He highlighted the risks posed to the autonomy of Horizon Europe by a 'common rule-book' with the European Competitiveness Fund. To alleviate this risk, and strengthen the autonomous foundation of Horizon Europe, Heitor listed 7 priorities:

- ▶ Reinforcing the European Research Council (ERC) financially and institutionally to enable its full independence. This includes doubling its current budget, preserving four-year presidential mandates, and maintaining it as a fully 'bottom up' and curiosity-driven instrument, with its governance overseen by the S&T board, free from "Commission priorities" in its programming.
- ▶ Reforms to address the factors that limit the European Innovation Council (EIC), such as overly short innovation cycles. This could include experimenting with new funding and assessment methods through an 'experimental unit'.
- ▶ Increasing the MSCA budget to € 25bn (from the current € 9b) and doubling the funds allocated to the ERC to successfully build 'Choose Europe' as a co-funding mechanism to promote research careers throughout European research institutions. MSCA and ERC applications from countries such as the United States have grown exponentially.
- ▶ The establishment of independent councils to govern collaborative research in Horizon Europe, following lessons learned from the ERC and the EIC. Collaborative research that addresses industrial competitiveness should be differentiated from that addressing emerging societal challenges; both should be governed through independent councils, which include technical, social, economic and policy experts. National governments should retain the jurisdiction over budgetary decisions, but the programme's management should be undertaken by these independent councils.
- ▶ Complementing Horizon Europe by effective schemes for European public procurement.

- ▶ Revisiting the Cohesion Policy in conjunction with FP10 to guarantee the expansion and focus on Widening initiatives in the 'Teaming programme', as well as refreshed programmes for research and technology infrastructures and university alliances.
- ▶ Collaborating globally in science and technology. A new nuanced and gradual approach to such co-operation is needed, alongside a refreshed approach to 'Global Europe' policy and funding. This should include the strengthening of specific global partnerships and include actions with institutions from the US, China, India, Brazil, Africa, and the Emirates. These should be oriented to foster strategic R&I partnerships throughout Europe, and be accompanied by a needed revision of the research security framework at project level.

Heitor recognised the EU's comparative funding weakness in global terms, and repeated his call for an increased budget. Referring to the most famous painting in the Munch Museum, the venue of the High Level Workshop, he called on the scientific community to "Scream" and to "be loud" in its advocacy efforts during this unique moment.

Lord Patrick Vallance

Through a video address, **Lord Patrick Vallance**, Minister of State in the United Kingdom's Department for Science, Innovation and Technology, confirmed the UK Government's commitment to global collaboration, growth, and security, and its objective to rebuild the country's reputation as a trusted partner. He noted Europe's role as key partner, illustrated by the UK's association to Horizon Europe.

Addressing the next Framework Programme, he reiterated the importance of excellence criteria in ensuring European security, sustainable prosperity, and competitiveness. He praised the MSCA and the ERC, and stressed the importance of fundamental research. Just a couple of decades ago, it would have been impossible to predict the implications of modern technologies such as Artificial Intelligence. The Framework Programme must therefore enable curiosity-driven research that prepares us for yet unseen developments. However, mission-driven research is also necessary and the programme must be a mix of investigator- and challenge-led research. Another essential characteristic of the programme should be its openness towards trusted partners, and Associated Countries must be able to fully participate from its start, rather than join at a later point.

Lord Vallance argued that ethics, research integrity, research security, sustainability, and inclusivity should not be seen as barriers to addressing global challenges, but as enablers of long-term success. He emphasised the importance of dialogue and learning from others through multilateral forums such as Five Eyes, the G7, the OECD, as well as via funder-level engagement through Science Europe. He concluded with a call for collaboration, praising the ability of democratic, like-minded countries to work together to deliver security, prosperity, knowledge, and benefits for citizens.

Oksen Lisovyi

Olga Polotska, Executive Director of the National Research Foundation of Ukraine, delivered an address on behalf of **Oksen Lisovyi**, Ukrainian Minister of Education and Science. He welcomed the European Commission's proposal for the next Framework Programme, and emphasised its integration of science, innovation, competitiveness, security, and resilience. He also highlighted the inclusion of dual-use technologies in the programme, citing it as a crucial innovation.

Minister Lisovyi also expressed the importance of being associated to the programme, and reiterated Ukraine's official announcement of intent to join the next Horizon Europe. This marks an important step in the country's integration into the European Research Area. Such a step forward, based on trust and collaboration, enables open, secure, equitable, and excellent research, he added.

The Minister's address further highlighted the establishment of the '[International Coalition for Science, Research and Innovation in Ukraine](#)' at the Ukraine Recovery Conference in Rome in July 2025. He thanked the European Commission, and the fourteen countries and numerous international organisations who already joined, and warmly invited all potential new partners.

He concluded by emphasising the need for joint efforts in building a European R&I ecosystem of trust, openness, and innovation. He highlighted that this future co-operation will be mutually rewarding, given the unique experiences of Ukraine that it is eager to share.

Plenary discussion

During the plenary discussion, participants and keynote speakers had the opportunity to elaborate on previously addressed topics. One of the key themes of the discussion was R&I driven by societal challenges. Manuel Heitor addressed the topic, highlighting that the key characteristic should be the 'political ownership' of innovation policy by those who are facing the challenge. However, as this is often not the case, funding is distributed too thin and wide – leading to less impact than having a limited number of excellent institutions receiving long-term funding. Ultimately, this limited the successes of missions, he argued. This stemmed from external political influence, which led to an outcome that was misaligned with their original design and purpose.

Keynote Speeches: Part 2

Javier Moreno Fuentes

In some cases, research collaboration is becoming a 'zero-sum' game: where someone wins, someone else loses. It is crucial that we make sure that international collaboration itself is not on the losing side, stated **Javier Moreno Fuentes**, Vice-President for International Affairs of the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC) and Vice-President of Science Europe. International collaboration presents a complicated equilibrium: making sure partnerships work and produce results, while maintaining our national security interests. The co-existence of research security and academic freedom cannot be taken for granted, he argued; recognising trade-offs is essential.

Moreno Fuentes presented the key findings of the [Science Europe Report on Research Security](#), which emphasises that academic co-operation must be safeguarded; we must not renounce collaboration entirely because of the presence of risk. Research must be carried out openly, equitably, and in a safe and secure environment that protects international collaboration, whilst acknowledging that there is no one single protocol that an organisation can follow, nor a blueprint to adhere to ensure that each collaboration is 'safe'. A space for the development of policies, mutual learning, guidance, and red lines should be created. The EU's efforts to strengthen research security, including embedding it into law, is welcome.

The complete elimination of risk would be an insurmountable task, he added. A more realistic approach is to minimise and manage it, while educating and engaging R&I communities on research security, emphasising their interest in protecting their knowledge and research. While one cannot dictate how individual researchers will approach their collaborations, they should be equipped with the requisite knowledge to plan how they are going to protect their research.

Moreno Fuentes acknowledged it was vital to protect the knowledge produced by our scientists through building capacity at national and funder levels and within organisations. This can be achieved by establishing mechanisms for dialogue, and repositories for case studies that can be shared to enable best practices. Science Europe is an ally in this objective, particularly in establishing a dialogue between national funders and helping to build capacity at all levels.

Lise Øvreås

Lise Øvreås, President of the European Academies Science Advisory Council (EASAC) addressed international collaboration and research security in the context of the Arctic. The region is not only a key priority for Norway, but also holds profound significance for the entire planet: there is increased global focus on it due to the emergence of new transportation routes resulting from climate change, competition for resources, and acute environmental vulnerability (temperatures are rising

four times faster in the Arctic than elsewhere in the world). This is set to have global repercussions; Øvreås emphasised that, due to the region functioning as a ‘cooling system’ for the planet, “what happens in the Arctic does NOT stay in the Arctic.”

Øvreås introduced participants to [The Arctic Council](#): an intergovernmental initiative established in 1996 between Canada, Denmark, Finland, Iceland, Norway, the Russian Federation, Sweden, and the United States. It promotes co-operation and co-ordination while managing sustainable development and environmental pollution. However, geopolitical tensions have weakened its political capacity, even if technical co-operation has resumed. Meanwhile, the involvement of non-Arctic European nations is growing in the region.

She shared a real-time example of how these geopolitical tensions impact research collaboration, through the EU-funded partnership [INTERACT](#) into permafrost research. This project consists of 74 field bases, but data can no longer be collected from those in Russian territories, which impacts monitoring in the region and research in the area as a whole. This highlights that research is no longer only about climate change, but also about sovereignty and survival; researchers need guidance on distinguishing between open and restricted data. There is a role for the EU to show leadership on data sharing.

Øvreås also highlighted the role of the [European Academies Science Advisory Committee \(EASAC\)](#), an Academy-led independent advisory body for science policy. It provides evidence-based advice on key European policies on deep sea mining, gas, Europe’s future in the Atlantic realm (eg. reviewing gulf streams and increasing temperatures), as well as on wildfires, where Europe faces growing risks due to their increasing frequency.

MEPs Christian Ehler and Lina Gálvez

Members of the European Parliament Christian Ehler and Lina Gálvez, representing its Committee on Industry, Research, and Energy (ITRE), contributed to the workshop. MEP Ehler addressed the audience through a video address, while MEP Gálvez joined the meeting online.

Christian Ehler was recently appointed as the European Parliament’s rapporteur for its report on the 10th EU Framework Programme for R&I, Horizon Europe, as well as

co-rapporteur for its report on the European Competitiveness Fund. He addressed the proposal from the European Commission in the context of a changing world: where one must adapt to new circumstances, a 'business as usual' approach will not suffice. He observed that the Commission proposes a shorter regulation, with less specific budget lines, more general wording on international co-operation, and that it does not contain sufficient guarantees for the autonomy of the ERC and the EIC.

He highlighted the Parliament's call for more clarity in these areas, as well as for the development of a strategic framework for decisions on international collaboration, as opposed to the current case-by-case basis. To avoid the risk of making one-off, ill-informed decisions, there needs to be a commitment to international co-operation with more clarity and structure.

Ehler called for a reform of the programme, emphasising the importance of agility, the need for expert governance, as well as novel ways to develop work programmes and defining calls. He referred to Mario Draghi's report to underscore the importance of establishing a programme that is managed by experts. Furthermore, he echoed Manuel Heitor's earlier calls for the involvement of independent councils in the programme's governance, highlighting this as a step in the right direction.

He posed the question to participants whether Europe needs independent research funding organisations like those that exist on national level. Highlighting the importance of RFOs a cornerstone of academic freedom, he argued that their mandates (including on research security) could be best achieved – and their close links with researchers best used – if they could make decisions independently from national governments.

Lina Gálvez was appointed as the Socialists & Democrats shadow rapporteur on the 10th EU Framework Programme for R&I. She addressed a number of key aspects that the Parliament would focus on in the upcoming inter-institutional dialogue.

The Parliament would aim to ensure that the programme is adequately funded. Although it welcomed the Commission's proposal, Gálvez noted that it might change during the trilogue discussions. She also highlighted the issue of contested trust in science, stressing that R&I can only thrive in a society that trusts it. The benefits of science, evidence, and knowledge-based policy making should be better demonstrated. In addition, R&I must find an equilibrium between openness, competitiveness, and research security. She called for the dialogue on secure R&I to continue, so as to achieve the right balance. Regarding innovation and valorisation, she underscored the importance of building bridges between academia and industry; this requires a common ecosystem to ultimately benefit society.

Gálvez also emphasised the importance of resilience in funding mechanisms and international collaboration, to mitigate the risks from global uncertainties. She welcomed the 'Choose Europe' initiative in this context, but added that emphasis should be placed on attracting (and retaining) early-career researchers, as well as involving them in the dialogue. Binding policies on equality, diversity, and inclusion would enable access to untapped potential.

She reaffirmed the European Parliament's commitment towards the best policy environment to advance Horizon Europe and the ERA, as well as towards enabling

transparent, collaborative, and innovation-driven policies to achieve the best results for our competitiveness and our capacity to maintain the European Union project and our democracies. To this end, she welcomed the open dialogue with the R&I community to improve the legislation.

Plenary Discussion & Conclusions of Day 1

BOTH PLENARY DISCUSSION SESSIONS addressed many of the issues raised by the speakers in both keynote sessions.

Øvreås responded to questions from the audience, confirming that Europe should be strongly motivated to engage in Arctic research, given its wider impact. Meanwhile, the restrictions on data, stemming from research security considerations can put researchers – especially student or early-career researchers – in a difficult position when engaging with Arctic research. Recalling the phrase ‘as open as possible, as close as necessary’, the conversation highlighted some key aspects relevant to research security: definitions, researcher education, values, and individual responsibilities.

Participants argued that the increasing cultural shift towards securitisation may make researchers overly cautious – especially if they lack knowledge on the security situation, or if there are no clear definitions. This dilemma should be solved by significantly increasing efforts to guide and train researchers on how to approach research security. Meanwhile, it is crucial that these efforts do not reduce scientists’ agency and autonomy; they should be involved in the development of this discussion from the start and have fora to enable exchange between themselves.

At the same time, it should be noted that research security guidelines would build on a set of established academic principles and values, closely linked to the ideals of the European Project. One must therefore be careful when thinking about changing such values systematically.

The related topic of dual-use research also arose in the discussions. Those familiar with policy developments confirmed that there is a lot of ambiguity regarding the term. Research outcomes are often uncertain, and a wide range of research has dual-use potential. In addition, the scope of dual use can go beyond technology directly applied in defence activities: knowledge itself can have a dual-use function.

Theme 1

Research Valorisation & Innovation

Opening keynote

- 🎤 **Eystein Jansen**, Vice-President of the ERC Scientific Council

Panel

- 🎤 **Anne Kjersti Fahlvik**, Executive Director of Innovation in Industry and the Public Sector at the Research Council of Norway (RCN)
- 🎤 **Lauma Muizniece**, Director of the Latvian Council of Science (LZP) [ONLINE]
- 🎤 **Josep M. Garrell**, President, European University Association
- 🎤 **Jesús Valero**, President of European Association of Research and Technology Organisations (EARTO)
- 🎤 **Pavlo Bazilinsky**, Executive Board member of Marie Curie Alumni Association

Moderator: **Javier Moreno Fuentes**, Vice-President for International Affairs, Spanish National Research Council (CSIC), Vice-President of Science Europe

Moreno Fuentes introduced the discussion by highlighting the importance of Horizon Europe for R&I in Europe. He posed questions about the overall prospects for the upcoming programme, its governance, financial aspects, and links to innovation, as well as its alignment with the European Competitiveness Fund.

Keynote Presentation

Eystein Jansen provided the keynote speech for this session. He recognised the success of the ERC, not only as a cornerstone of researcher-driven and fundamental research, but also in driving European competitiveness, with many ERC grantees leading innovation projects, founding start-ups, and holding patents. Although the ERC's budget is almost doubled in the European Commission's proposal (it represents 17% of the programme's total budget), this increase is comparatively less than the expansion of the budget for innovation. Furthermore, concerns remain about whether the ambitious proposed ERC budget will 'survive' the trilogue negotiations. This could have dire consequences for the ERC: given the 20–25% increase in applications, the success rate may drop to under 10%. Furthermore, Jansen highlighted that the award sum has remained unchanged since 2007 – which, due to inflation, has significantly reduced its purchasing power.

He reinforced the ERC's commitment to continue funding frontier research across all fields based on excellence, while reinforcing its governance to ensure scientific freedom and institutional autonomy. However, he voiced concerns on whether the proposal sufficiently safeguards the Council's autonomy and institutional freedom, which are crucial for attracting and retaining talent, and ensuring scientific excellence. He in particular drew attention to the proposal of the European Commission to reduce the term for the ERC Chair from four to two years, as well as the concept of the 'common rulebook'. He stressed that true independence for the Council should be enabled by establishing the ERC as a Union body with its own regulation. This would give it the ability to devise its own strategy, and guarantee its researcher-led governance, with clear roles and responsibilities. In addition, this guarantee should not require renewal every seven years alongside the introduction of new Framework Programmes and the Multiannual Financial Framework.

Jansen also touched upon science diplomacy, advising careful openness with like-minded countries amid a complex geopolitical landscape. He noted that targeted collaboration helps prevent 'freezedown' and supports Europe's strategic positioning in areas like the Arctic.

Panel Discussion

Setting the scene and evaluating the Horizon proposal

The continuity between the structures of the current and new Horizon Europe, as well as the general direction of the latter were welcomed. Many of the speakers noted that the increased funding was a positive development – with some caveats. The increased budget may remain insufficient and, while the programme remains standalone, some of its links with the European Competitiveness Fund place its autonomy at risk.

The panellists provided a wide variety of perspectives, with **Jesús Valero** asserting that the positive aspects of the Commission's proposal outweigh the negative, as they support the research-to-innovation pipeline, and thus, boost competitiveness.

Autonomy and links with the European Competitiveness Fund

Speakers highlighted the need for a distinct legal structure regarding the programme's autonomy. Some considered the removal of the civilian clause and the potential introduction of directionality into the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) to be concerns.

Pavlo Bazilinskyy called for strong support for research careers – at least €25bn for MSCA - in addition to a curiosity-driven, transparent Horizon Europe that enables open science by adopting Diamond Open Access and the CoARA principles for the reform of research assessment. This resonated with many of the panellists arguing for the protection of bottom-up and excellence-driven instruments and for maintaining Horizon Europe's focus on lower Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs). They also explored the possible opportunities and benefits from the link with the ECF with regards to valorisation, and addressed the need for prioritisation in light of resource limitations.

Balanced governance, and managing complexities

Panellists underscored the importance of excellent basic science in maintaining a full R&I continuum – having industry, start-ups, scale-ups, and researchers appropriately connected, rather than putting overt emphasis on any of these themes.

Josep M. Garrell called for changes in the legal framework and reiterated the need for academic career assessment reform as an example. He recommended an approach that balances Commission priorities, universities' needs, and reasonable links between fundamental research and innovation, enabling universities to engage the entire innovation pipeline.

In finding such equilibrium, the often different 'industrial policy logic' must be contrasted with 'research logic'. This calls for layered governance structures, and cross-cutting mechanisms. However, complex architectures and fragmented policy structures can be overwhelming – especially in the case of countries with limited administrative capacity. This is the case in many Eastern European states, such as Latvia, emphasised **Lauma Muižniece**. Navigating such structures requires skills; to develop these, countries with less resources must rely on international knowledge flow, the maintenance of which is crucial.

Valorisation and Collaboration

Speakers emphasised the importance of mechanisms that convert excellent science into competitiveness and societal benefits. To this end, institutions must enable commercialisation, even if not all scientists wish to be entrepreneurs, said **Anne Kjersti Fahlvik**. In this context, Pillar 2 is a strategically important instrument for

Norway and Europe's established industries. She highlighted the example of the maritime industry and the collaboration between companies and research institutes, as well as practical AI applications for navigation and ship design.

Further addressing Pillar 2, the role of applied research and market needs within it were emphasised by Valero. Collaboration for its own sake is not viable, he stated. Sprawling, multi-partner projects have limited impact, which would be improved by vertical, fast-track innovation pathways and industry involvement in governance, according to EARTO. Furthermore, the increase in the budget of Pillar 2 is comparatively lower than other pillars, which poses additional issues.

Noting the importance of start-ups and scale-ups, the significant enlargement of the budget of Pillar 3, as well as the connection to other funds such as the European Investment Bank was welcomed. However, linking research infrastructures with technology infrastructures in Pillar 4 may bring about financial uncertainties.

Conclusions

The session concluded with agreement on the need for balance between research excellence, innovation, and competitiveness. Autonomy, openness, and collaboration were emphasised as essential principles for Europe's future research and innovation landscape.

Proposals for the next Framework Programme and the ECF present significant opportunities, but also challenges – particularly for smaller actors. Continuous dialogue and stakeholder engagement will be crucial to ensure effective implementation. Responsible openness and science diplomacy should remain central to European research policy.

During the conversation, speakers converged on the need to:

- ▶ safeguard ERC autonomy and streamline implementation
- ▶ further develop avenues for multifaceted collaborations in Pillar 2
- ▶ ensure mechanisms that translate excellent science into economic and societal impact
- ▶ support research careers and open science
- ▶ pursue responsible openness and science diplomacy with likeminded partners

Theme 2

Shaping the Future of Research

Opening keynotes

- ▶ **Alejandro Adem**, President of Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council of Canada (NSERC), Chair of the Governing Board of Global Research Council (GRC) (*online*)
- ▶ **Katja Becker**, President of the German Research Foundation (DFG)

Panel

- ▶ **Mario Cervantes**, Senior Economist at Organisation for Economic Co-Operation and Development
- ▶ **Joe O'Hara**, President of European Alliance for Social Sciences and Humanities (EASSH)
- ▶ **Pil Maria Saugmann**, President of European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers (EURODOC)
- ▶ **Thomas Alslev Christensen**, Senior Vice President, Novo Nordisk Fonden

Moderator: **Lidia Borrell-Damián**, Secretary General, Science Europe

Lidia Borrell-Damián set the stage for the discussion. She emphasised the importance of the upcoming Horizon Europe programme and the need for a broader, long-term vision for European research. She highlighted the importance of stakeholder engagement, cross-sectoral collaboration, and the need for policies that foster both innovation and societal benefit.

Keynote speeches

Alejandro Adem emphasised the necessity of global collaboration to address complex challenges such as clean energy, climate resilience, and global health. He highlighted that impactful research requires the engagement of diverse partners worldwide, ensuring that all voices, regardless of geography, gender, or socio-economic status, are included. Equity and diversity are essential for building trust and accountability in research outcomes, as it allows us to build 'communities of trust'. Research undertaken in this way can better respond to international challenges, and can become a "bridge between national interests and global responsibilities."

He underscored the importance of open science in preventing science from becoming insular, and disconnected from its purpose. Nevertheless, he acknowledged the increasing risks - including from cybersecurity threats, and misuse or targeting of sensitive research outputs - which may pose a credible threat to the integrity of the research ecosystem that prizes openness. He recalled the adage 'as open as

possible, as closed as necessary', acknowledging its frequent usage and highlighting that openness and safety can be complementary. He used the example of Arctic research to underline the need for collaborative, interdisciplinary, and inclusive approaches, particularly involving Indigenous communities and knowledges. He also noted the region's geopolitical importance given its richness in strategic resources, and its key role in the management of the climate crisis.

Adem also addressed the growing impact of artificial intelligence on research – and the parallels with the discourse on closed- vs. openness. He stressed the need for a responsible, transparent, and internationally collaborative adoption of AI, while remaining vigilant about risks to scientific rigour and data privacy. Furthermore, he addressed the development of the notion of excellence – with which research assessment must develop in parallel to keep pace.

He welcomed the decision that Canada can be a part of Horizon Europe. While acknowledging the historical differences between European states and Canada, he called for the programme to provide enough clarity to set the path for collaborations across the globe.

Katja Becker highlighted Horizon Europe and the ERA Act as policy instruments that will define the framework conditions for research in Europe and its partner countries over the coming decade and beyond. She outlined three core principles for thriving European research systems that should also guide the negotiations on Horizon Europe and the ERA Act: excellence, openness, and trust.

With regard to the negotiations on the next Framework Programme, she stressed that while the Commission envisions a direct link between research and competitiveness, the Framework Programme must remain clearly distinct from industrial policy. Scientific excellence, she argued, is the true foundation of Europe's competitiveness: "innovation begins with the curiosity of excellent researchers."

The autonomy and bottom-up nature of programmes like the ERC and MSCA must be preserved, she stated. She highlighted how a number of German institutions, including the DFG, are exploring the concept of an 'ERC for institutions', responding to a suggestion in the Draghi report. She also warned against narrowing the scope of research by focusing too heavily on competitiveness and commercialisation –

highlighting how 90% of the collaborative research budget in Pillar 2 is directed towards its 'competitiveness' component.

Openness, particularly to global collaboration, Becker argued, is vital for Europe's research success. Cautioning against excluding non-EU partners from collaborative research, she called for greater flexibility in association policies, as well as a strong differentiation between association to Horizon Europe and the ECF.

She also addressed the increasing emphasis on research security, advocating guidance, self-governance, and academic freedom rather than over-regulation. Becker highlighted the practical aspect of increasing the resilience of research systems and data. She emphasised that Europe must not respond to threats with "structural mistrust." Trust, she concluded, is what distinguishes Europe's research systems, and maintaining public trust and institutional autonomy – while guaranteeing academic freedoms, and researcher-led, peer review-based methods – is crucial for resilience and excellence.

"Where politics divides, science can connect," she said, highlighting that collaboration does not only address urgent global challenges but also builds robust networks and long-standing partnerships. For this, an overarching framework on science diplomacy could help guide and safeguard co-operation in times of geopolitical tension.

Panel discussion

Data-driven insights into R&I collaboration, and avenues for policy responses

Mario Cervantes initiated the discussion, sharing insights from the recent [OECD Science, Technology and Innovation Outlook 2025](#). The data show that while research intensity has increased over the past decade, the rate of growth has slowed and government allocations for R&D have declined in most areas except energy and defence. He noted a similar duality in collaborative R&I: a decrease in international collaboration – particularly between the US and China, but also within the EU and other regions – alongside the prevalence of an appetite for talent attraction.

He identified the securitisation of R&I as one of the potential causes, as the number of countries with formal research security policies has risen sharply in recent years. In addition to researchers, industry, and public and private funders, it is also necessary to engage with the diplomatic community, especially as geopolitical issues increasingly intersect with science and innovation. Panellists also pointed out a link between the working conditions of researchers and research security, in particular concerning those from third countries who may face increased precarity due to tightening legislation on immigration.

A landscape defined by geographical and stakeholder connections

While the trend may show a reduction in collaboration, the panel reflected the increasingly global nature of the research ecosystem, compared to the 1980s and '90s. Despite the emerging challenges facing collaboration, participation from

researchers outside Europe has increased and there is a greater emphasis on societal impact, which goes hand-in-hand with excellence. This should be a priority for not only society, but industry as well, noted **Thomas Alslev Christensen**.

Enterprise foundations, such as his organisation, fund research institutions and universities, rather than companies directly. This approach provides grounds for collaboration that benefits both companies and public research performing organisations. Therefore, the industrial perspective is not limited to commercialisation, but also refers to knowledge and the identification of breakthrough potential.

It was argued that this must have implications on politics: instead of contrasting industrial and research policies, we should further develop our understanding on what is research policy. While links exist in strategic priorities and R&I, planning how to exploit these must be improved – and this is often initiated from the research side, the panellists noted.

Inclusion, interdisciplinarity, and values

The panellists underscored the importance of foresight and the need to stand by values and principles, including in institutional autonomy and ethics, when engaging internationally. The key 'democratic mission' of higher education was addressed: reinforcing values, and fostering co-creation. This, however, is not without difficulties, as highlighted by the experiences of Eurodoc (the European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers) in designing its own programme. Education on research values must provide a broad perspective, and underscore the value of knowledge.

Researchers alone cannot respond to multifaceted challenges: all stakeholders – local and regional governments, universities, research institutions, civil society, and especially early-career researchers – must be involved in shaping research policy. However, (post-)doctoral researchers are often excluded from policy discussions, which can lead to the perception of structural mistrust and missed perspectives. Representing early-career researchers, **Pil Maria Saugmann** argued passionately for broader inclusion.

The panellists emphasised not only the link between research, education, and society, but pointed out that researchers themselves are members of society and thus part of an interconnected system. This calls for an interdisciplinary approach that enables conversations between different epistemologies, and a mindset change that enables the co-design of such a system. The social sciences, humanities, and arts (SSHA) should play the role of co-architects in such an endeavour, rather than be considered as an afterthought, said **Joe O'Hara**.

The panel noted that the precarity of researchers is also detrimental to the key value of academic freedom. If researchers lack resources, then their freedom of enquiry is blocked. In this context, career structures for early-career researchers and good organisational cultures are crucial parts of a values-based approach to research.

Community roles, and societal dimensions at heart

The panel considered there to be a social dimension to almost every major research topic (such as trust, security, innovation), noting that a fundamental characteristic of all research is societal wellbeing. This makes the integration of SSHA relevant at every stage of the research process, from design to implementation.

Research outcomes should align with societal values. Different communities and ways of thinking are therefore necessary in the different stages of the (non-linear) research process. This would create coherence in communicating the value of research and could contribute to eliminating mistrust as well as harmful disinformation, such as in the case of vaccine-scepticism. Yet, SSHA faces financial uncertainties, as opposed to mission-oriented research, given the resource-intensive nature of social sciences, despite some common misperceptions.

Conclusions

The panel members emphasised the convergence of novel technologies and their policy implications in the future of research. To this end, they highlighted the need for dialogue between scientists (and in particular early-career researchers), policy makers, diplomats, and all elements of society to ensure mutual understanding and effective policy development.

All panellists advocated higher quality in research proposals and underscored the foundational principles of openness, excellence, transparency, collaboration, and security, as well as the involvement of SSHA in all research activities.

They called for a long-term vision for research and the need for early commencement of policy conversations, rather than waiting for formal evaluations or political cycles.

Thematic Group Discussions

IN THE PARALLEL DISCUSSION SESSIONS, senior leaders and experts from Science Europe Member Organisations, as well as invited participants, had the opportunity to share their views in more detail and further address the themes introduced during the keynotes and panel discussions:

- ▶ Horizon Europe and its links to other programmes
- ▶ International collaboration
- ▶ International collaboration and the equilibrium between openness and security

All participants were also asked to provide their input on different aspects of the Horizon Europe proposal and outline actionable recommendations that Science Europe and its membership could carry out.

Outcomes

All groups highlighted the need for clarity with regard to the connections between Horizon Europe and other programmes, particularly the European Competitiveness Fund. The need to define competitiveness in a broad sense, as outlined in Science Europe's November 2025 [position on the connection between the programmes](#), was reiterated. The conversations focused heavily on Pillar 2, as a significant part of this pillar (and thus, collaborative R&I within Horizon Europe) will take place at the intersection with the ECF, within the shared policy windows. Some discussions revolved around the funding ratio of competitiveness- and societal challenge-related R&I in Pillar 2, with some participants expressing concerns about the imbalance between the two, as the former component receives a significantly larger part of the budget.

In addition, questions emerged on how to connect the different 'logics' of each instrument, as the ECF will likely adopt a more industrial approach that will have to be aligned with the research-based foundations of Horizon Europe. In line with this, participants highlighted that the 'seamless funding model' that justifies the links, does not necessarily guarantee balanced decision making. To ensure the best

results for R&I in this context, it was concluded that the governance and tools for implementation should be developed and remain within the jurisdiction of Horizon Europe.

To make such policies viable, participants highlighted that the importance and critical value of research – including curiosity-driven R&I – must be clearly demonstrated. Science Europe could contribute to this through advocacy. Furthermore, to bring the different philosophies of competitiveness and research closer together, the full integration of SSHA into Pillar 2 was recommended.

On a more practical note, some participants focused on the proposed topics of the policy windows, as well as potential areas that may fall between the gaps, and not be covered. Noting the possibility of unforeseen challenges (or possibilities), the policy windows need to be flexible and/or there must be a possibility to add additional priorities. Meanwhile, some members of the groups noted that the vagueness surrounding the links leaves stakeholders in a 'grey zone'. Although there was a clear intent to provide recommendations, it was hard to define how to advise on planning and implementation without more concrete details and experiences.

Addressing international collaboration, there was a consensus on the indispensability of the association model, and the key role that Associated Countries play in Horizon Europe. In light of the links between the Framework Programme and the ECF, the need for clarity and regulatory certainty for Associated Countries was reiterated. Rather than raising further complexities – such as making association to the ECF a prerequisite for participation in collaborative R&I – many participants in the discussion groups argued that the association process should be simplified, and in particular faster.

The arguments ran parallel with those on Associated Countries' access to the programme: participants noted the risk that further barriers may be raised as a consequence of Horizon Europe's connection to the ECF, while associated partners would ideally have full access. They underlined that this is not only beneficial for Associated Countries, but also for the EU. Furthermore, the question of Associated Countries' involvement in the Framework Programme's governance was raised. Participants acknowledged the important role of Science Europe in representing the

interests of its members from Associated Countries, and called on the organisation to continue its advocacy on this issue.

With regards to wider collaboration, the definition of the widely used term 'like-minded' – or the lack thereof – was addressed. Some participants recommended linking the concept with academic freedom. Furthermore, participants discussed whether 'like-minded' should be used in context of countries, or whether it should be applicable to individual collaborators as well.

The underlying purposes of collaboration were also discussed. Building on the statement from the earlier panel, "collaboration for its own sake [is] not viable," participants highlighted what makes international collaboration essential: its ability to build and reinforce valuable connections; its strengthening of all partners, even in cases where a competitive element is also present; and, its delivery of impact with added value, that would have not been possible without each partner.

When discussing research security and openness, participants noted that 'tensions' are likely here to stay. Nevertheless, these discussions should be continuously maintained to reconcile opposing views. Participants proposed that this dialogue should be underpinned by values (although this can be challenging in the current geopolitical environment), as partners who are considered trusted, may place limitations on academic freedoms.

The participants acknowledged the role of research funding and performing organisations in raising awareness, and called for the continuation and increase of such activities. The roles and responsibilities of researchers themselves should be defined, while there is also a desire for EU-level guidance. This guidance should recognise the different approaches that may be necessary, depending on the country or research topic. Horizon Europe can contribute to this exercise, given that the countries associated to it represent a pool of trusted partners. Both awareness-raising activities and guidance should make use of the significant experiences and competences gathered in Ukraine. In addition, debates on research security on the national and EU level must be linked: the EU dimension, and collaboration within Horizon must be considered when addressing national research security issues.

Meanwhile, as the participants noted, in face of the significant push towards securitisation, it is crucial that the fundamental values that openness creates, do not disappear. Openness provides a wide range of perspectives that are essential for addressing multifaceted global challenges. To this end, the promotion of these values is important on the institutional level. At EU level, maintaining openness could become an advantage, if other global players favour limiting collaboration. However, regarding innovation, the importance of the local dimension should also be considered: some of the participants called for a rational approach to global openness that does not undermine local/regional competitiveness.

Finally, the contributors highlighted some practical issues closely linked to secure openness where further discussion is necessary. Firstly, cybersecurity is essential; however, as some participants pointed out, it heavily relies on private actors, which may also pose a security risk. Secondly, it is important to consider the implications of openness on intellectual property rights as well.

Conclusions

THE 2025 HIGH LEVEL WORKSHOP ignited timely discussions on the role of research in an international environment of changing geopolitical paradigms. The case study of polar research illustrated the necessity of maintaining open international collaboration in a secure way and provided some best practices on how to conduct it effectively. This connected directly to policy discussions on the next Framework Programme, Horizon Europe, currently being developed. It must address new political priorities – such as the EU’s competitiveness – while supporting excellent research and innovation and maintaining global scientific co-operation.

Key messages from the workshop, presented in the December 2025 [Concluding Statement](#), show that these themes are interconnected and should be approached from different perspectives. Competitiveness must be understood more broadly as regenerative and sustainable growth in the long term, rather than as a set of short-term economic priorities.

A robust R&I ecosystem that enables curiosity-driven and fundamental research is essential to support this broader notion of competitiveness. Such a system must be autonomous and responsibly self-governed. Researcher-driven policies should build the scientific and technological base of the EU, supported by appropriate high-level guidance. While Horizon Europe activities can support other programmes – most notably the European Competitiveness Fund – the programme must retain sufficient autonomy and jurisdiction over its policy tools to prioritise excellent science. This system must be co-developed by governments of Member States and Associated Countries, research funding and performing organisations, and researchers at all career stages.

This ecosystem must enable and actively advocate open collaboration responsibly, while recognising necessary compromises to ensure research security. This is a challenging task that extends beyond R&I priorities alone. As demonstrated by polar research, research and innovation, geopolitical interests, and global challenges often intersect and must be balanced carefully.

Interconnectedness is also a key factor in global collaboration. Reinforced connections are needed to withstand geopolitical pressures and address global challenges such as the climate crisis. All disciplines – including Social Sciences, Humanities and Arts – are critical for this and should be integrated horizontally.

Associated Countries are indispensable in strengthening global collaboration, including within Horizon Europe. Science Europe will therefore advocate their full participation in the programme without arbitrary barriers, together with a smooth association process.

These conclusions highlight the key themes and their links to each other. Thanks to the contributors and participants, the High Level Workshop was an excellent example of how these links can be explored via dialogue between a diverse range of stakeholders – a dialogue that must be continuously maintained. Future discussions should build on these exchanges to shape an R&I ecosystem that serves and benefits society as a whole.

Annex

Workshop Programme

WEDNESDAY 19 NOVEMBER

The Munch Museum - Festsal // Edvard Munchs plass 1, 0194 Oslo

14.00–14.15 Welcome and Addresses by Hosts

Mari Sundli Tveit

President of Science Europe and Chief Executive of the Research Council of Norway (RCN)

Christopher Smith

Governing Board Member of Science Europe and Executive Chair of the Arts and Humanities Research Council, UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)

14.15–15.30 High-level Keynotes – Part I

Sigrun Aasland

Minister of Research and Higher Education of Norway

Signe Ratso

Deputy Director-General for Research and Innovation, European Commission

Manuel Heitor

Chair of the Expert Group on the Interim Evaluation of Horizon Europe, Author of the report 'Align, Act, Accelerate'

Lord Patrick Vallance (*video address*)

Minister for Science, Innovation, Research and Nuclear of the United Kingdom

Oksen Lisovyi

Minister of Education and Science of Ukraine
*Presentation delivered by **Olga Polotska**, Executive Director of the National Research Foundation of Ukraine*

PLENARY DISCUSSION

MODERATOR

Lidia Borrell-Damián

Secretary General of Science Europe

RAPPORTEUR

Márton Kottmayer, Science Europe

15.30–16.00 *Coffee Break*

16.00–17.30 **High-level Keynote Presentations – Part II**

PRESENTATION OF SCIENCE EUROPE REPORT ON RESEARCH SECURITY

Javier Moreno Fuentes

Vice-President of Science Europe and Vice-President for International Affairs of the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)

KEYNOTE PRESENTATION

Lise Øvreås

President of the European Academies Science Advisory Council (EASAC)

Short Q&A session on both presentations

POLICY KEYNOTES

Christian Ehler (*video address*)

Member of the European Parliament Committee on Industry, Research, and Energy (ITRE)

Lina Gálvez (*online*)

Member of the European Parliament Committee on Industry, Research and Energy (ITRE)

PLENARY DISCUSSION AND WRAP-UP OF DAY 1

MODERATOR

Christopher Smith

RAPPORTEUR

Georgina Drury, UK Research and Innovation

THURSDAY 20 NOVEMBER

The Munch Museum - Festsal // Edvard Munchs plass 1, 0194 Oslo

09.00–10.15 Theme I: Research Valorisation & Innovation

KEYNOTE SPEECH

Eystein Jansen

Vice-President of the ERC Scientific Council

PANEL DISCUSSION

Anne Kjersti Fahlvik

Executive Director of Innovation in Industry and the Public Sector at the Research Council of Norway (RCN)

Lauma Muižniece (*online*)

Director of the Latvian Council of Science (LZP)

Josep M. Garrell (*online*)

President of the European University Association (EUA)

Jesús Valero

President of the European Association of Research and Technology Organisations (EARTO)

Pavlo Bazilinskyy

Executive Board Member of the Marie Curie Alumni Association (MCAA)

MODERATOR

Javier Moreno Fuentes

RAPPORTEUR

Lillian Baltzrud, Research Council of Norway

10.15–11.15 Coffee & Breakout Discussions

Discussions in four breakout groups on both themes.

1

MOD. Anna di Ciaccio, National Institute for Nuclear Physics (INFN)

RAP. Diana Potjomkina, Science Europe

2

MOD. Krzysztof Józwiak, National Science Centre (NCN)

RAP. Tom-Espen Møller, Research Council of Norway (RCN)

3

MOD. Anu Noorma, Estonian Research Council (ETAG)

RAP. Márton Kottmayer, Science Europe

4

MOD. Sybille Wentker, Austrian Academy of Sciences (OeAW)

RAP. Aimée Allsopp, UK Research and Innovation

11.15–12.30 **Theme 2: Shaping the Future of Research**

KEYNOTE SPEECHES

Alejandro Adem (*online*)

President of the Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council of Canada (NSERC), Chair of the Governing Board of the Global Research Council (GRC)

Katja Becker

President of the German Research Foundation (DFG)

PANEL DISCUSSION

Mario Cervantes

Senior Economist at the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD)

Joe O'Hara

President of European Alliance for Social Sciences and Humanities (EASSH)

Pil Maria Saugmann

Former President of the European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers (Eurodoc)

Thomas Alslev Christensen

Senior Vice President of the Novo Nordisk Foundation

MODERATOR

Lidia Borrell-Damián

RAPPORTEUR

Julie Christiansen, Research Council of Norway

12.30–12.45 **Report from Breakout Discussions**

 Rapporteurs from breakout sessions

12.45–13.00 **Closing Statements**

Mari Sundli Tveit

Christopher Smith

The ERA refers to a unified European Research Area in which researchers are free to move around, perform their research, and work together with researchers from other countries.

Creating the ERA requires the harmonisation of various rules, requirements, and regulations, and closer international collaboration within the EU.

The High Level Workshop on ERA offers an annual platform for Science Europe Member Organisations, national ministries, and EU institutions to discuss progress, specific aspects, and future development of the ERA.

Science Europe, UK Research and Innovation, and the Research Council of Norway organised the 2025 edition of the High Level Workshop on the European Research Area with the support of the Norwegian Ministry of Education and Research.

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